

Heritage Buildings and Objects Digitisation & Visualisation within the Cloud

<https://heritalise-ecch.eu/>

This is part of the project that has received funding from the European Commission Horizon Europe Programme under Grant Agreement no. 101158081

This is part of the project that has received funding from UK Research and Innovation – Innovate UK under Innovation Funding Service (ISF) 10147707, 10135283 and 10147532

HERITALISE mission is to research and develop advanced digitisation techniques and solutions for documenting and representing diverse CH assets, giving a full comprehension of the diverse CH features, visible and non-visible.

The **Cultural Heritage Cloud** or **European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH)** is a European Union initiative to create a shared digital infrastructure that connects cultural heritage institutions and professionals across the EU. It will provide specific digital collaboration tools for the sector while removing barriers for smaller and more remote institutions.

The Cultural Heritage Cloud aims to add a digital dimension to cultural heritage preservation, conservation, restoration, and enhancement by providing cutting-edge technology for artefact digitisation and artwork research. The goal is to assist cultural heritage institutions and research organisations of all sizes, and both professionals and non-professionals, in managing their digital objects more effectively. The Cultural Heritage Cloud will facilitate this through enhanced visibility, interconnectivity, and access to scientific resources, training, and advanced digital tools. These tools will help them navigate the challenges posed by the digital transition in the cultural heritage sector.

Through Horizon Europe, the Commission has allocated a significant budget (around €110 million) to fund innovative projects that contribute to enrich the Cultural Heritage Cloud by developing tools and services to digitise, preserve and valorise Europe's cultural heritage. Visit the European Commission page to learn more or download the official flyer (412kb).

This page lists all the projects funded by the European Union that, together with ECHOES, contribute to the creation of the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

Objectives

HERITALISE mission is to research and develop advanced digitisation techniques and solutions for documenting and representing diverse CH assets, giving a full comprehension of the diverse CH features, visible and non-visible.

Review & Protocols: Assess and define current digitization standards, methodologies and data requirements for tangible and intangible CH objects. Address gaps, set objectives and assess risks.

Advanced Data Acquisition: Enhance 2D/3D technologies (e.g., LiDAR, photogrammetry) with improved calibration, metrology and multimodal capabilities for scalable, high-quality digitization.

AI-Powered Post-Processing: Develop AI-driven workflows, data fusion and algorithms to streamline post-processing, integrating tangible and non-tangible data for conservation insights.

HW/SW Solutions: Create tools (e.g., 3D printing, VR/AR platforms, Geo-HBIM) to enhance CH engagement, accessibility and real-time monitoring of digitized assets.

Interoperability & Sharing: Develop open components for seamless data integration across CH databases (e.g., Europeana), leveraging APIs, semantic standards and metadata.

Impact & Dissemination: Address tech transfer challenges, standardize web platforms and showcase digitization applications via 4 proof-of-concept use cases.

The Impacts

Museums in XXI century are spaces that must include digital experiences in their temporary or permanent exhibitions, thanks to a creative reuse of collections or documents. In this sense, the impact of this project can be crucial.

Enhanced intervention speed and maintenance optimization for Cultural Heritage Preservation and enhanced preservation effectiveness - By leveraging digital heritage data, we will achieve a **40% faster intervention speed and optimized maintenance** for cultural heritage preservation, minimizing risks of irreversible damage. Our methods will enhance preservation by enabling precise detection of hidden issues, improved geometric accuracy, and advanced analysis through HBIM and data fusion. This approach will also **eliminate the need to dismantle heritage objects**, ensuring complete safety during evaluations.

Will enable 2,000 heritage professionals to collaborate in new ways, benefit 100 stakeholders and reach up to 10 million users. By advancing digitization and exhibitions, it **will enhance museum engagement with collections and audiences**, while also aligning heritage work with Sustainable Development Goals to support education, economy, and society.

Will provide **70% greater, more democratic access** to a distributed, FAIR-based software ecosystem and data. It will also deliver **50% cost savings** in maintenance and monitoring, significantly enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of preservation planning.

This initiative will enable heritage professionals to **engage audiences more deeply**, fostering learning and community connections, while **facilitating collaborative networks** across Europe and beyond.

Will enhance digitization accuracy, enabling digital twins to authentically represent heritage objects. This advancement will support heritage organizations, boost tourism and education, and strengthen European identity. Key impacts include **promoting the green transition, fostering social cohesion, and safeguarding cultural assets for future generations**.

Digitizing cultural heritage and integrating it into the European Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) will **improve access for museums across Europe**, making resources discoverable and contextually enriched. This will enable curators to create diverse, thematic exhibits, **fostering cultural understanding** and promoting social inclusion, unity, and EU values.

Supports the EU's Green Deal goals by contributing to monitoring, adaptation, mitigation, and communication efforts to address the climate emergency. Developing innovative ways to share these digital records **fosters remote collaboration, reducing the need for travel and mitigating climate impact**. Digital representations of at-risk heritage will also allow organizations to create impactful exhibits, engage the public, and inspire action to combat the climate emergency.

Supports the European Bauhaus goals by enhancing access to digital heritage through the ECCCH. It aims to enrich lives, promote sustainability, and foster inclusivity across cultures and disciplines. By improving digitization and providing detailed metadata, the initiative will **enable digital heritage to inspire creativity and contribute to the New European Bauhaus movement**.

The Pillars

The HERITALISE project proposes the development and implementation of different technologies and solutions. Six pillars have been organised to replicate and scale up these solutions across Europe.

HERITALISE includes 4 demonstration centres in 3 different countries with the aim of further scalability and replication of the researched technological solutions.

West Highland Museum, Fort William, Scotland

Partners: WHM, USTAN

Building type: Category B listed

Potential outreach: 90,000 in person visitors per year, 200 heritage practitioners

Use case:

- Digitisation of the Jacobite and Carmichael collections and the building
- New digital exhibits for the museum, website and app to showcase landscapes, buildings, artworks and Gaelic cultural heritage
- Digital exhibits available through VR kiosks offering both touchscreen and immersive headset experiences

Timespan Museum, Highlands, Scotland

Partners: HHAS, USTAN

Building type: Museum and landscape

Potential outreach: Small museum and art gallery with international standing

Use case:

- VR Room: Timespan's new digital venue for hosting HERITALISE partners, developing VR/AR technologies for CH objects and showcasing exhibits using VR, Xbox and touchscreens
- Timespan Object Collection: offers HERITALISE a testbed for visualizing objects and artifacts, even incomplete ones, to study environmental and social changes across Europe
- Kildonan Landscape: a unique open-air museum with archaeological sites spanning 6,000 years, showcasing human occupation through varied historic remnants
- Helmsdale Fishing Village & Jurassic Coastline: A historic 1815 fishing village with VR models depicting its 1890s peak during the herring boom, reflecting Scotland's trade history
- Community & Museum Sector Engagement: Collaborative virtual events held in 2020 featuring digital models, 3D objects, and films, including virtual tours and reconstructions of historical sites like Helmsdale Castle and Iron Age settlements

Reggia di Venaria Reale, Turin, Italy

Partners: CCRS, CCR, POLITO

Building type: UNESCO site

Potential outreach: strong outreach potential by serving as a testing ground for new digital technologies in CH audience engagement

Use case:

- **Building Digitization:** Multiscale, multisensor scans of the Reggia di Venaria Reale, focusing on St. Uberto Church and the Great Gallery, to support maintenance and enhance visitor experience
- **Architectural Analysis:** 3D surveys and historical documents will reveal structural and hidden details of the Church and Gallery, monitoring conditions like humidity and microclimate that affect artwork preservation
- **Landscape Heritage:** Digital tracking of Giuseppe Penone's Gardens of Fluid Sculptures to capture the dynamic aging process of this blend of art and nature.
- **Object Documentation:** 3D imaging and tomography of 18th-century furniture to study cabinet-making techniques and monitor degradation due to environmental factors

Villa Portelli, Kalkara, Malta

Partners: HM

Building type: Historic villa

Potential outreach: 300,000 visitors per year; tens of international stakeholders, restorers, companies

Use case:

- **Oral History Digitisation:** Record memories of former VP workers, especially around significant changes in the villa's landscape
- **Building Digitisation:** Document the entire villa for conservation and as a BIM model and digital twin, usable at other heritage sites
- **Methodology Testing:** Combine techniques like LIDAR, photogrammetry, laser scanning, and Reflective Transformation Imaging to capture detailed site data
- **Public Outreach Tools:** Experiment with VR/AR, holograms, and projections to engage Gen Z audiences and study their interactions with digital heritage tools

Consortium

Politecnica di Torino

<https://heritalise-ecch.eu/>

Funded by the European Union

This is part of the project that has received funding from the European Commission Horizon Europe Programme under Grant Agreement no. 101158081

This is part of the project that has received funding from UK Research and Innovation - Innovate UK under Innovation Funding Service (ISF) 10147707, 10135283 and 10147532